

Mixed-Ligand Complexes : Part VI. Acetoacetanilidato bis (Biguanide) Cobalt (III), N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylaminato bis (Biguanide) Cobalt (III) and 2-Picolylaminebis (Biguanide) Cobalt (III) Salts.

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Acetoacetanilide (AcanH) and N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (BphaH) react readily with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ {BigH=biguanide) to form the mixed chelates $[\text{Co}(\text{Acan})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{Bpha})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$. Compared to tris (biguanide) cobalt (III) absorption spectra shift considerably to the red. Attempts at resolution have failed.

A mixed chelate, 2-picolylamine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) has also been obtained. A spectral study indicates 2-picolylamine occupying a position intermediate between ethylenediamine and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl in the spectrochemical series. The complex could not be resolved.

Some of the earlier papers in the series have covered reports on the syntheses, characterisation and resolution of a series of mixed chelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ (AA = $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl, o-phenanthroline, alkylbiguanides, 1-amidino-O-alkylureas)¹ and of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AB})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ (AB = acetylacetonate ion, 8-hydroxyquinolate ion).² In this paper we describe two more mixed chelates of the second type using acetoacetanilide or N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine as the third participating ligand around cobalt (III). Acetoacetanilide and other members of the acetoacetanilide family are only recently being investigated as complexing ligands.^{3,4} The present study appears to be using N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine, the versatile organic analytical reagent⁵, for the first time in a mixed chelate system.

Both these ligands react with diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) to liberate ammonia. When the crude diammine base is used as the starting material, the impure base of the mixed chelates separate as voluminous mass. These are converted to the chloride salts, which are further purified by crystallisation from aqueous solution in the cold. A few salts, chloride, bromide, sulphate, nitrate and the d-camphorsulphonate have been characterised.

The molar conductance values of 240 mhos for the acetoacetanilide complex and 244 mhos for the N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine complex are close to those generally found for the bi-univalent electrolytes (225-270 mhos). The equivalent weights evaluated by the ion-exchange technique are close to those deduced from analyses and conductance measurements.

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1. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 832, 842.
2. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 853.
3. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 381.
4. A. Syamal and R. L. Dutta, *This Journal*, 1968, 45, 1 ; *Indian J. Chem.* 1968, 6, 520.
5. S. C. Shome, *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 4, 107 ; B. Das and S. C. Shome, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1965, 32, 52.

TABLE I

Conductance and Equivalent Weight Data

Complex	Molar Conductance (ohms ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Equivalent Weight	
		Found	Reqd.
1. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	240	253	250
2. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	244	285	283
3. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₃]I ₃ ·2.5H ₂ O	444	—	—
4. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₃](SO ₄) _{1.5} ·3H ₂ O	—	185	188

The electronic spectra reveal two absorption bands as usual⁶. In both the mixed chelates the ¹T_{1g}←¹A_{1g} band (I) is shifted considerably to the longer wave length compared to tris (biguanide) cobalt (III). In this regard these two complexes are akin to acetylacetonatobis (biguanide) cobalt (III)², thus indicating that acetylacetonate, acetoacetanilide and N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine ions are closely spaced in the spectrochemical series.

The d-camphorsulphonate salts of both the mixed chelates were prepared characterised and fractionated from aqueous solution. None of these fractions showed any rotation substantially higher than what may have arisen from the active anion. The d-tartrate salts in both the series tended to become sticky and impure.

2-Picolylamine (Picam), structurally intermediate between ethylenediamine and αα'-dipyridyl, has been introduced as a chelating agent a few years ago⁷. More extensive spectral studies have indicated that the 2-picolylamine chelates are intermediate between those of the ethylenediamine and αα'-dipyridyl chelates.⁸ This strong field character of the ligand prompted us to undertake the synthesis of the mixed chelate [Co (Picam) BigH₃]₃³⁺ and to study the properties thereof.

TABLE II

Electronic Spectra of Cobalt (III) Mixed Chelates

Complex	Band I	Band II	Reference
	ν(cm ⁻¹)(ε)	ν(cm ⁻¹)(ε)	
1. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	19800-20000(167)	27000(447)	This study
2. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	19600 (207)	27000(440)	..
3. [Co(Acac)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	20000 (177)	29400(160)	2
4. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	21000-21300(177)	—	This study
5. [Co(en)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	20000-21000(165)	—	Unpublished studies
6. [Co(dipy)(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	21300-21500(172)	30300(1145)	1
7. [Co(BigH) ₃]Cl ₂	21000 (235)	28200-28600(220)	1

The ligand reacts as expected to form the desired heterochelate. However, the salts being quite soluble we have succeeded in isolating only the sulphate, iodide and the cobaltinitrite. Conductance measurements on the iodide salt and equivalent weight of the sulphate salt have established the tri-univalent character of the complex entity.

6. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, 1967, p 875.
7. G. Sutton, *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1960, **13**, 74, 222, 473 ; 1961, **14**, 37, 545 ; 1962, **15**, 232.
8. Utsuno and Sone, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1964, **37**, 1038.

The electronic spectra of the chloride salt (obtained from the sulphate by the action of barium chloride) shows that the first band is intermediate between those of ethylenediamine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl bis (biguanide) cobalt (III). The second band however is covered by a strong absorption arising out of 2-picolylamine in the ultraviolet.

The d-tartrate salt being extremely soluble in water, oily fractions were collected by progressive addition of acetone, oils triturated repeatedly with acetone to a solid consistency and any possible rotation measured. We did not have any evidence of resolution being effected.

Attempts to obtain a heterochelate with 8-aminoquinoline did not materialise.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) base was obtained as described previously in this series². Acetoacetanilide was a B. D. H. product and N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine was obtained following standard procedure⁹, 2-Picolylamine was a product of Columbia Organic Chemicals.

Acetoacetanilidato bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) chloride: Diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) base (1.03 g.) suspended in water (20 ml) was treated with an alcoholic solution of acetoacetanilide (0.53 g in 10 ml) and the mixture triturated for an hour at room temperature. The chocolate coloured precipitate was collected, washed with water, suspended in water (15 ml) and neutralised with dilute HCl. The solution was immediately filtered and cooled in ice. The crystals were further purified at room temperature from 1 : 1 alcohol-water mixed solvent.

The sulphate salt was obtained by treating a saturated aqueous solution of the above chloride salt with ammonium sulphate solution. The bromide salt was obtained using KBr. Ammonium d-camphorsulphonate immediately produces voluminous precipitate which tends to become sticky. This was repeatedly scratched with acetone to a powder.

The N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine chelates were obtained similarly.

2-Picolylamine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) sulphate: The diammine bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) base (1.03 g) suspended in water (20 ml) was treated with 2-picolylamine (0.32 g) in 10 ml water. The mixture was digested on a steam bath to a faint smell of ammonia, neutralised with dilute H_2SO_4 , concentrated (5 ml) and allowed to crystallise in the frigidaire. The product was further purified by recrystallisation from water.

The iodide salt was obtained after neutralisation of the above reaction product with dilute HCl and precipitating with KI in the cold. The cobaltinitrite was

9. S. C. Shome, *Analyst*, 1950, 75, 28.

obtained as yellow crystals on the addition of sodium cobaltinitrite to the chloride salt. The d-tartrate salt was obtained by carrying the above neutralisation with d-tartaric acid followed by acetone. The oily product was repeatedly scratched with acetone to a solid form. This was further dissolved in water and the process repeated.

TABLE III

Characterisation Data of the Chelates

	% Cobalt	% Nitrogen	% Anion
1. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₂]Cl ₂	Found : 11.51 Reqd : 11.6	Found : 30.2 Reqd : 30.3	Found : 13.7 Reqd : 14.0
2. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₂]SO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	Found : 9.5 Reqd : 9.2	Found : 24.3 Reqd : 24.1	Found : 15.2 Reqd : 15.0
3. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₂]Br ₂	Found : 10.2 Reqd : 9.9	Found : 25.6 Reqd : 25.9	Found : 26.9 Reqd : 27.0
4. [Co(Acan)(BigH) ₂](CS) ₂	Found : 6.8 Reqd : 6.5	Found : 17.3 Reqd : 17.1	— —
5. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₂]Cl ₂	Found : 10.2 Reqd : 10.4	Found : 28.5 Reqd : 28.3	Found : 12.6 Reqd : 12.5
6. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₂]SO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Found : 8.7 Reqd : 8.5	Found : 22.4 Reqd : 22.2	Found : 13.7 Reqd : 13.9
7. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Found : 9.4 Reqd : 9.6	Found : 29.8 Reqd : 29.6	— —
8. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₂]Br ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	Found : 8.4 Reqd : 8.7	Found : 22.7 Reqd : 22.8	Found : 23.5 Reqd : 23.4
9. [Co(Bpha)(BigH) ₂](CS) ₂	Found : 6.7 Reqd : 6.4	Found : 16.8 Reqd : 16.5	— —
10. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₂](SO ₄) ₁₋₂ ·3H ₂ O	Found : 10.2 Reqd : 10.4	Found : 29.3 Reqd : 29.7	Found : 25.3 Reqd : 25.5
11. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₂] ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	Found : 7.3 Reqd : 7.4	Found : 21.4 Reqd : 21.2	Found : 47.8 Reqd : 48.1
12. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₂] [Co(NO ₃) ₂] ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	Found : 15.8 Reqd : 15.7	Found : 33.9 Reqd : 33.7	— —
13. [Co(Picam)(BigH) ₂](d-tart) ₁₋₂ · 3H ₂ O	Found : 8.9 Reqd : 9.1	Found : 26.3 Reqd : 26.0	— —

The hydration contents were determined by loss at 120° and confirmed to the formula given. CSH=d-camphorsulphonic acid ; d-tart=d-tartrate anion.